

Mineral and chemical composition of the high-sulfidation epithermal Cu-V-Sn-As assemblage in the Assarel porphyry copper deposit, Central Srednogie

Dimitrina Dimitrova¹, Elitsa Stefanova¹, Atanas Hikov¹, Stoyan Georgiev¹, Irena Peytcheva¹, Ventsislav Stoilov², Desislav Ivanov², Milen Stavrev¹

¹ Geological Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia 1113, Bulgaria; E-mails: didi@geology.bas.bg; ahikov@geology.bas.bg; elitsa.s@gmail.com; kantega@abv.bg; ipeytcheva@geology.bas.bg

² Assarel Medet JSC, 4500 Panagyurishte, Bulgaria; E-mails: vstoilov@asarel.com; divanov@asarel.com

Минерален и химичен състав на високосулфидизираната епитермална Cu-V-Sn-As парагенеза в медно-порфирно находище Асарел, Централно Средногорие

Димитрина Димитрова¹, Елица Стефанова¹, Атанас Хиков¹, Стоян Георгиев¹, Ирена Пейчева¹, Венцислав Стоилов², Десислав Иванов², Милен Ставрев¹

Abstract. Assarel porphyry copper deposit is located in the Panagyurishte ore district, Central Srednogie, which is a part of the Late Cretaceous Apuseni–Banat–Timok–Srednogie magmatic and metallogenic belt. This study reports a new data on the epithermal high-sulfidation ore mineralization described previously as “specific” and “rare”. The ore mineralization is associated with advanced argillic alteration and is represented by enargite, colusite, sulvanite, bornite. They occur as thin veinlets brecciating or crosscutting earlier small disseminated euhedral/subhedral to anhedral pyrite in quartz or subhedral/anhedral pyrite nest-like aggregates with zunyite, gypsum, rutile. Bornite is replaced by chalcocite and covellite, and enargite by covellite. Enargite contains Sn, Sb, Te, while colusite occurs as two distinct chemical varieties: 1) Sn-rich and Mo-bearing, with lower As content, and 2) Sn-poor, Ge-bearing, As-rich. Both varieties have 0.1–0.2 wt% Sb. Bornite and chalcocite contain small amounts of Se. Pyrite spatially associated with this mineralization is enriched in Cu, Co, and Ni, with Co/Ni and Co/As ≥ 2 .

Keywords: epithermal mineralization, trace and critical elements, Assarel porphyry Cu deposit, AGEMERA.

Introduction

The porphyry copper deposits (PCD) are main source for Cu, Mo, and Re worldwide and may carry significant content of Au. Other strategic and critical metals in the PCDs, such as W, Bi, In, Te, Se, and Ag also can be extracted as by-products. Bismuth, Au, Ag, Te, Se, Sn, In, W, Mo, As, Sb are concentrated during late porphyry system evolution within intermediate- to high-sulfidation epithermal mineralizations, usually in the upper levels of the system (Sillitoe, Hedenquist, 2003; Sillitoe, 2010). Rare high-sulfidation style min-

eralizations were described for both Assarel and Medet Cu porphyry deposits in the Panagyurishte ore district, Central Srednogie, Bulgaria (Strashimirov, 1982; Petrunov et al., 1991; Strashimirov et al., 2002; Popov et al., 2012; Cioacă et al., 2020). They are represented by fine-grained enargite, goldfieldite, colusite, arsenosulvanite, sulvanite, aikinite, wittichenite, hessite, occurring as euhedral crystals, anhedral aggregates, and veinlets (enargite, colusite) or oval inclusions in earlier pyrite.

This study presents new data on the epithermal high-sulfidation assemblage, its mode of occurrence

and chemical composition of the main minerals based on new findings in the Assarel deposit.

Geological setting

Presently in Bulgaria, two of three world-class porphyry Cu deposits, located in the Panagyurishte ore district are still mined, namely the Assarel and Elat-site deposits. Mining of the third porphyry deposit Medet ceased in 1996. The Panagyurishte ore district, Central Srednogorie (Bulgaria) is a part of the Late Cretaceous Apuseni–Banat–Timok–Srednogorie (ABTS) magmatic and metallogenic belt (Popov et al., 2002). The ABTS belt formed as a result of the subduction of the Tethyan oceanic crust under the European continental margins that generated the Upper Cretaceous volcano-plutonic complexes and associated ore deposits (Dabovski et al., 1991; Popov et al., 2002; von Quadt et al., 2005). The Assarel deposit (~91 Ma) (Zimmerman et al., 2008) is a part of the Assarel-Medet magmatic structure that consists of the Assarel stratovolcano, and numerous diorite, and granodiorite intrusive bodies and dykes, which intruded Upper Cretaceous volcanic rocks and the Variscan basement (Strashimirov et al., 2002; Kamenov et al., 2007; Nedialkov et al., 2007). Assarel volcanic and porphyritic rocks belong to the calc-alkaline and high-K calc-alkaline series, and their geochemical characteristics are typical of enriched mantle source, indicating a subduction-related volcanic-arc setting (Nedialkov et al., 2007; Kamenov et al., 2007). The volcanic and plutonic rocks that host the Assarel deposit were affected by intensive hydrothermal alterations. Propylitic, argillic, sericitic, and advanced argillic alteration types are established, as well as transitional alteration types – propylite-argillic, propylite-sericitic, argillic-sericitic, and sericite-advanced argillic (Bogdanov, 1987; Kanazirski et al., 2000; Strashimirov et al., 2002; Hikov, 2013, and references therein). Calcite-zeolite and anhydrite-gypsum late alterations are defined as post-ore (Bogdanov, 1987). Several hydrothermal ore mineral assemblages have been identified (Bogdanov, 1987; Petrunov et al., 1991; Strashimirov et al., 2002): quartz-magnetite-hematite; quartz-pyrite-chalcopyrite; quartz-molybdenite; quartz-pyrite; quartz-galena-sphalerite; calcite-zeolite; and the supergene covellite-chalcocite and malachite-azurite±Fe-hydroxide.

Materials and methods

The samples used in this study were obtained during field campaign at the Assarel PCD in the frame of a Horizon Europe project called AGEMERA: “Agile Exploration and Geo-modelling for European Critical Raw Materials”. The mineralogy and petrography of the samples were determined by optical microscopy in transmitted and reflected light. Mineral composition was examined using JEOL JXA-8530F electron probe microanalyzer in the laboratory for electron microanalysis at the Earth Science Institute, Slovak Academy of Sciences, located in Banská Bystrica, Slovakia.

Trace element contents in pyrite, bornite, and enargite were measured by laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) on polished sections at the Geological Institute (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences), Sofia, Bulgaria. The analyses were made using the PerkinElmer ELAN DRC-e ICP-MS equipped with a New Wave UP193-FX excimer laser ablation system. NIST SRM 610 glass and USGS MASS1 were used as external standards. The laser system was operated at a constant 4–6 Hz pulse rate; laser energy density was 6.0–7.0 J/cm² on the sample using a 35 µm spot size. The following isotopes were monitored: ⁴⁹Ti, ⁵¹V, ⁵³Cr, ⁵⁵Mn, ⁵⁷Fe, ⁵⁹Co, ⁶⁰Ni, ⁶⁵Cu, ⁶⁶Zn, ⁷¹Ga, ⁷⁴Ge, ⁷⁵As, ⁷⁷Se, ⁹⁵Mo, ¹⁰⁷Ag, ¹¹¹Cd, ¹¹⁵In, ¹¹⁸Sn, ¹²¹Sb, ¹²⁵Te, ¹⁸²W, ¹⁸⁵Re, ¹⁹⁷Au, ²⁰²Hg, ²⁰⁵Tl, ²⁰⁸Pb, and ²⁰⁹Bi. Data reduction was done using SILLS ver. 1.1.0 software (Guillong et al., 2008), and Fe and Cu as internal standards.

Results and discussion

In the studied samples, the epithermal high-sulfidation assemblage mostly occur as thin veinlets brecciating or crosscutting earlier disseminated euhedral/subhedral to anhedral pyrite or nest-like aggregates of subhedral/anhedral pyrite, quartz, zunyite, gypsum, rutile. It is mainly represented by enargite and colusite (Fig. 1a–d). Both minerals are also present as euhedral platy (enargite) and subhedral (colusite) crystals with size from ~50 µm to ~150–200 µm, separately or together disseminated in quartz (Fig. 1a, b). Enargite forms thicker veinlets (up to ~500–700 µm). Colusite subhedral crystals and aggregates show distinct zonation (Fig. 1b). In some samples, colusite occurs as veinlets with sulvanite and bornite with size up to 25 µm (Fig. 1c, d). Larger bornite aggregates with chalcopyrite exsolution lamellae and submicron-sized inclusions of Se-bearing galena (Fig. 1f) sometimes associate with colusite-bornite veinlets. It seems that they are a bit earlier or simultaneously formed with colusite-bornite. Partial replacement of bornite by chalcocite of these veinlets is also observed (Fig. 1e). The replacement of bornite by chalcocite and enargite, and colusite by covellite in some samples is more advanced.

Chemical composition of enargite shows variable contents of Sn, Sb, and Te (Fig. 1g). The composition of colusite is more diverse (Fig. 1h). In the zoned subhedral crystals, where colusite occurs with enargite, microprobe data show significant enrichment in Sn in the central part (6–9 wt%) at the expense of As (6–8 wt%) and Sn-poor rim (0.4 wt%). This colusite is also enriched in Mo (0.44–0.76 wt%) but has very low Ge content (<100 ppm).

On the other hand, colusite occurring with bornite in association with pyrite, zunyite, gypsum, and quartz is Sn-poor (150–3000 ppm), contains Ge up to 0.5 wt% and has higher As content. Petrunov et al. (1991) reported enrichment of Sn in colusite and occurrence of arsenosulvanite replacing colusite. In this study, the Sn-poor colusite has chemical composition very similar to that reported for arsenosulvanite by Petrunov et al (1991). It is also formed after the Sn-enriched colusite.

Fig. 1. Mineral associations (*a–f*) and chemical composition of enargite, colusite, bornite, and pyrite (*g–l*). *a*, thin veinlet of colusite and enargite enveloping earlier pyrite in quartz; *b*, colusite grain showing distinct zoning with rutile and pyrite in quartz; *c*, colusite-bornite veinlet crosscutting earlier pyrite-zunyite; *d*, colusite-bornite-sulvanite veinlets crosscutting earlier subhedral pyrite crystal aggregates; *e*, colusite-bornite chalcocite veinlet crosscutting pyrite-zunyite aggregates; *f*, bornite veinlet with chalcopyrite exsolution lamellae and Se-bearing galena inclusions crosscutting and enveloping earlier pyrite; *g–i*, range of trace element contents in enargite, colusite and bornite; *j–l*, trace element contents and established Pearson correlation coefficients in pyrite. Abb.: *Bn*, bornite; *Cc*, chalcocite; *Ccp*, chalcopyrite; *Col*, colusite; *Eng*, enargite; *Gn*, galena; *Gp*, gypsum; *Py*, pyrite; *Qz*, quartz; *Rt*, rutile; *Sul*, sulvanite; *Zun*, zunyite.

Study of Spry et al. (1994) on the crystal chemistry and structure of colusite and arsenosulvanite from different localities postulated that arsenosulvanite is actually colusite and consequently the mineral was discredited by IMA (Burke, 2006). However, Sn-free colusite with composition close to the ideal chemical formula $\text{Cu}_{24}\text{V}_2\text{As}_6\text{S}_{32}$ was reported from many localities: Lorano and Calagio (Italy) and Gies (Montana, USA) (Spry et al., 1995); Pefka (Greece; Repstock et al., 2015); Lebedinoe (Russia; Nenasheva, Karpenko, 2010); As-sarel (Bulgaria, Petrunov et al., 1991; this study) and

others. Based on chemical and X-ray powder data, Nenasheva and Karpenko (2010) argued that further structural study of “arsenosulvanite” should be carried out because its discreditation was incorrect. So far, Mo concentrations in colusite were not reported, although in colusite-type synthetic derivatives Mo occupies the *A* site in the structure, where V is contained (Guélou et al., 2021). Thus, further investigation on colusite chemistry is necessary to outline the two varieties.

The LA-ICP-MS analyses of bornite show limited content of trace elements (Fig. 1i). Only Se concentra-

tion reaches up to 1000 ppm. The measured contents of Bi, Pb, and Ag vary in wide range and based on the estimated Pearson correlation coefficient they are probably related to inclusions of Pb-, Bi- and Ag-bearing minerals. Chalcocite also contains limited content of trace elements, mainly Se (50–800 ppm) and Fe (40–5600 ppm).

Trace element composition of the spatially associated pyrite (earlier) was also examined. Elevated contents of Cu and Co are registered (Fig. 1j, k), but the established positive correlation between Co and Cu is slightly weak ($r = 0.35$). The positive correlation between Co and Ni is much stronger ($r = 0.90$, Fig. 1j) with Co/Ni and Co/As ratios usually above 2. The measured contents of Pb and Bi are related to inclusions (Fig. 1l).

Conclusions

The new find of the high-sulfidation epithermal Cu-V-Sn-As mineralization at the Assarel PCD reveals a potential for its wider distribution than previously reported. The aggregates are relatively larger and occur with advanced argillic alteration. In addition to previously reported data, LA-ICP-MS and EPMA analyses revealed that enargite is enriched in Sn, Sb, and Te. Colusite occurs in two distinct generations, earlier Sn-rich, Mo-bearing, with lower As content and late – Sn-poor, Ge-bearing. Bornite and chalcocite have some contents of Se. The spatially associated earlier pyrite is enriched in Cu, Co, and Ni. Most of the measured Bi and Pb concentrations in the analyzed minerals are related to submicron-sized mineral inclusions. Further studies on mineral relations, hydrothermal alteration, and trace element composition of both ore and gangue minerals will be necessary in order to explain the complex structural and ore-forming evolution of the Assarel deposit.

Acknowledgements: This study was supported by the AGEMERA project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement 101058178. The authors are grateful to Geoins Consult Ltd. for the provided help with sample collection.

References

Bogdanov, B. 1987. *Copper Deposits of Bulgaria*. Sofia, Technika, 388 p. (in Bulgarian with English abstract).

Burke, A. I. J. 2006. A mass discreditation of GQN minerals. – *Can. Mineral.*, 44, 1557–1560; <https://doi.org/10.2113/gscanmin.44.6.1557>.

Cioacă, M.-E., M. Munteanu, E. Lynch, N. Arvanitidis, M. Bergqvist, G. Costin, D. Ivanov, V. Milu, R. Arvidsson, A. Iorga-Pavel, K. Högdahl, V. Stoilov. 2020. Mineralogical setting of precious metals at the Assarel porphyry copper-gold deposit, Bulgaria, as supporting information for the development of new drill core 3D XCT-XRF scanning technology. – *Minerals*, 10, 946; <https://doi.org/10.3390/min10110946>.

Dabovski, C., A. Harkovska, B. Kamenov, B. Mavrudchiev, G. Stanisheva-Vassileva, Y. Yanev. 1991. A geodynamic model of the Alpine magmatism in Bulgaria. – *Geologica Balc.*, 21, 4, 3–15; <https://doi.org/10.52321/GeolBalc.21.4.3>.

Guélou, G., P. Lemoine, B. Rœau, E. Guilmeau. 2021. Recent developments in high-performance thermoelectric sulphides: an over-

view of the promising synthetic colusites. – *J. Mater. Chem. C.*, 9, 773–795; <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0TC05086E>.

Guillong, M., D. L. Meier, M. M. Allan, C. A. Heinrich, B. W. D. Yardley. 2008. Appendix A6: SILLS: A MATLAB-based program for the reduction of laser ablation ICP-MS data of homogeneous materials and inclusions. – In: Sylvester, P. (Ed.), *Laser Ablation ICP-MS in the Earth Sciences: Current Practices and Outstanding Issues*. Vancouver, B. C., Mineralogical Association of Canada Short Course, 40, 328–333.

Hikov, A. 2013. Geochemistry of hydrothermally altered rocks from the Asarel porphyry copper deposit, Central Srednogie. – *Geologica Balc.*, 42, 1–3, 3–28; <https://doi.org/10.52321/GeolBalc.42.1-3.3>.

Kanazirski, M., M. Gorova, I. Queralt. 2000. Metasomatic formations in the shallow parts of the Asarel porphyry copper deposit, Central Srednogie. – *Geochem. Mineral. Petrol.*, 37, 65–76 (in Bulgarian with English abstract).

Kamenov, B., Y. Yanev, R. Nedialkov, R. Moritz, I. Peytcheva, A. von Quadt, S. Stoykov, A. Zartova. 2007. Petrology of Upper Cretaceous island-arc ore-magmatic centers from Central Srednogie, Bulgaria: Magma evolution and paths. – *Geochem., Mineral. Petrol.*, 45, 39–78.

Nedialkov, R., A. Zartova, R. Moritz. 2007. Magmatic rocks and evolution of the Late Cretaceous magmatism in the region of the Asarel porphyry copper deposit, Central Srednogie, Bulgaria. – *Rev. Bulg. Geol. Soc.*, 68, 1–3, 46–65.

Nenasheva, S., V. Y. Karpenko. 2010. Features of arsenosulvanite from the Lebedinoe deposit, Central Aldan. – In: Novgorodova, M. I. (Ed.), *New Data on Minerals*. Publ. Inst. Russ. Acad. Sciences, Fersman Mineral. Museum RAS, 45, 50–59.

Petrunov, R., P. Dragov, H. Neykov. 1991. Polyelemental (with As, Sn, V, Bi, Ag, Te, Ge, Se, etc.) mineralizations in Assarel porphyry copper deposit. – *Rev. Bulg. Geol. Soc.*, 52, 1, 1–8 (in Bulgarian with English abstract).

Popov, P., T. Berza, A. Grubic, D. Ioane. 2002. Late Cretaceous Apuseni-Banat-Timok-Srednogie (ABTS) magmatic and metallogenic belt in the Carpathian-Balkan orogen. – *Geologica Balc.*, 32, 2–4, 145–163; <https://doi.org/10.52321/GeolBalc.32.2-4.145>.

Popov, P., S. Strashimirov, K. Popov, M. Kanazirski, K. Bogdanov, R. Radichev, S. Dimovski, S. Stoykov. 2012. *Geology and Metallogeny of the Panagyurishte Ore Region*. Sofia, University of Mining and Geology Press, 227 p. (in Bulgarian with extended English abstract).

Repstock, A., P. Voudouris, U. Kolitsch. 2015. New occurrences of watanabeite, colusite, “arsenosulvanite” and “Cu-excess” tetrahedrite-tennantite at the Pefka high-sulfidation epithermal deposit, northeastern Greece. – *N. Jb. Miner. Abh.*, 192, 2, 135–149; <https://doi.org/10.1127/njma/2015/0276>.

Sillitoe, R. H. 2010. Porphyry copper systems. – *Econom. Geol.*, 105, 1, 3–41; <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsecongeo.105.1.3>.

Sillitoe, R. H., J. W. Hedenquist. 2003. Linkages between volcanotectonic settings, ore-fluid compositions, and epithermal precious metal deposits. – In: Simmons, S. F., I. Graham (Eds.), *Volcanic, Geothermal, and Ore-Forming Fluids: Rulers and Witnesses of Processes within the Earth*. Society of Economic Geologists, Special Publication, 10, 315–343; <https://doi.org/10.5382/SP.10.16>.

Spry, P. G., S. Merlino, S. Wang, X. Zhang, P. R. Buseck. 1994. New occurrences and refined crystal chemistry of colusite, with comparisons to arsenosulvanite. – *Am. Mineral.*, 79, 750–762.

Strashimirov, S. 1982. Sulvanite and colusite from the molybdenum-copper deposit Medet. – *Geochem., Mineral. Petrol.*, 15, 57–66 (in Bulgarian with English abstract).

Strashimirov, S., R. Petrunov, M. Kanazirski. 2002. Porphyry-copper mineralization in the central Srednogie zone, Bulgaria. – *Mineral. Deposita*, 37, 587–598; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00126-002-0275-6>.

Von Quadt, A., R. Moritz, I. Peytcheva, C. Heinrich. 2005. 3: Geochronology and geodynamics of Late Cretaceous magmatism and Cu–Au mineralization in the Panagyurishte region of the Apuseni–Banat–Timok–Srednogie belt, Bulgaria. – *Ore Geol. Rev.*, 27, 1–4, 95–126; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oregeorev.2005.07.024>.

Zimmerman, A., H. J. Stein, J. L. Hannah, D. Koželj, K. Bogdanov, T. Berza. 2008. Tectonic configuration of the Apuseni-Banat-Timok-Srednogie belt, Balkans-South Carpathians, constrained by high precision Re-Os molybdenite ages. – *Miner. Deposita*, 43, 1–21; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00126-007-0149-z>.